

Academic Library as Scholarly Publisher Bibliography

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HOUSTON: DIGITAL SCHOLARSHIP

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Introduction

The *Academic Library as Scholarly Publisher Bibliography* includes over 175 selected English-language articles, books, and technical reports that are useful in understanding the digital scholarly publishing activities of academic libraries since the late 1980's, especially their open access book and journal publishing activities. The bibliography covers the following subtopics: pioneering academic library publishing projects in the 1980's and 1990's, early digital journals and serials published by librarians (as distinct from libraries), library-based scholarly publishing since the *Budapest Open Access Initiative*, technical publishing infrastructure, and library and university press mergers/partnerships and other relevant works.

Here is the Library Publishing Coalition's [definition of library publishing](#):

The LPC defines library publishing as the set of activities led by college and university libraries to support the creation, dissemination, and curation of scholarly, creative, and/or educational works.

Generally, library publishing requires a production process, presents original work not previously made available, and applies a level of certification to the content published, whether through peer review or extension of the institutional brand.

Based on core library values, and building on the traditional skills of librarians, it is distinguished from other publishing fields by a preference for Open Access dissemination as well as a willingness to embrace informal and experimental forms of scholarly communication and to challenge the status quo.

Starting in the late 1980's, university libraries were among the first publishers of digital scholarly journals on the Internet. With the approval and support of Robin N. Downes, the Director of the University of Houston Libraries, [The Public-Access Computer Systems Review](#), an open access journal, was launched in August 1989, with the [first issue](#) being published in January 1990. In November 1990, the Virginia Tech University Libraries [published](#) the [first issue](#) of the [Journal of the International Academy of Hospitality Research](#). The Stanford University Libraries [established](#) the [HighWire Press](#) in 1995, publishing *The Journal of Biological Chemistry* as its first journal. As of March 2015, HighWire Press had published over 2.4 million open access articles out of a total of 7.6 million articles. Again with Downes' approval, the University of Houston Libraries began publishing the [Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography](#), an open access book, in October 1996. This digital book was updated 64 times between 1996 and 2006 (Digital Scholarship continued its publication though [version 80](#) in 2011).

In the 1990's, digital journal and serial publishing projects that involved university libraries working in partnership arrangements included the [BioOne Project](#) (the University of Kansas, the Big 12 Plus Libraries Consortium, and other partners), [Project Euclid](#) (Cornell University Library and Duke University Press), [Project Muse](#) (Johns Hopkins University Press and the Milton S. Eisenhower Library), and [RLG DigiNews](#) (the Research Libraries Group and the Cornell University Library Department of Preservation and Conservation).

Early digital journals and serials published by librarians included the [Arachnet Electronic Journal on Virtual Culture](#), [Ariadne](#), [Current Cites](#), [Information Research](#), [Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship](#), [The Katharine Sharp Review](#), [LIBRES](#) (early volumes), [MC Journal: The Journal of Academic Media Librarianship](#), and [Public-Access Computer Systems News](#). (See the [Directory of Electronic Journals, Newsletters and Academic Discussion Lists](#), 6th edition and section [3.1 Electronic Serials: Case Studies and History](#), of the [Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography](#) for further information on this topic.)

In the 1990's, University libraries also acted as important digital journal publishing testing grounds for major academic publishers in ventures such as the [CORE Project](#), the [Red Sage Project](#), the [SuperJournal Project](#), and the [TULIP Project](#). (See section [3.3 Electronic Serials: Electronic Distribution of Printed Journals](#) of the [Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography](#) for further information on this topic.)

In the 1990's, a few library organizations and companies published electronic journals and serials. The Library Information Technology Association published [Telecommunications Electronic Reviews](#) and OCLC published [The Online Journal of Current Clinical Trials](#).

In the last 20 years, there has been a growing movement by academic and other libraries to directly publish books, journals, and other works. This resurgent activity has been fueled by the open access movement, which is typically viewed as starting with the 2002 [Budapest Open Access Initiative](#). Academic libraries built organizational and technical infrastructure to support this movement, often using open source software that was created in order to advance it. An increasing commitment to the OA movement sparked important cultural changes in libraries, which resulted in the proliferation of institutional repositories, scholarly communication units, and research data support units supported by them.

Open source software from the [Public Knowledge Project](#), such as [Open Journal Systems](#), is frequently used in library-based publishing programs; however, a variety of software tools, are also employed. Promising new open source publishing programs, such as [Fulcrum](#), [Hypothesis](#), [Janeway](#), [Manifold](#), and [PubPub](#), are emerging; but are not well represented in the types of works covered by this bibliography.

University presses are in a period of change and restructuring. Increasingly, they are being put under the administrative control of university libraries. Furthermore, entirely new all-digital open access university presses are being established, often under the direction of or in partnership with university libraries.

Coverage

The *Academic Library as Scholarly Publisher Bibliography* primarily covers published articles and books about the digital scholarly publishing activities of academic libraries since the late 1980's, especially their open access publishing activities. Its focus is on the publication of digital scholarly books and journals. Some included works may treat a broader scope of academic library digital publishing activities. Readers interested in detailed coverage of data publication issues may find the author's [Research Data Curation and Management Bibliography](#) helpful.

With a few historical exceptions, this bibliography does not include digital media works (such as MP3 files), editorials, e-mail messages, interviews, letters to the editor, presentation slides or transcripts, unpublished e-prints, or weblog postings. Coverage of conference papers and technical reports is very selective. Commercial software and other specialized software used by university presses are not covered by this bibliography.

Most sources have been published from January 2002 through July 2021; however, a limited number of earlier key sources are also included. The bibliography has links to included works. Such links, even to publisher versions and versions in disciplinary archives and institutional repositories, are subject to change. Where possible, this bibliography uses Digital Object Identifier System (DOI) URLs.

Abstracts are included in this bibliography if a work is under a Creative Commons Attribution License (BY and national/international variations), a Creative Commons public domain dedication (CC0), or a Creative Commons Public Domain Mark and this is clearly indicated in the work (see the "Note on the Inclusion of Abstracts" below for more details).

Dedication

In memory of [Paul Evan Peters](#) (1947-1996), founding Executive Director of the Coalition for Networked Information, whose visionary leadership at the dawn of the Internet era fostered the development of scholarly electronic publishing.

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1.0 Pioneering Academic Library Publishing Projects in the 1980's and 1990's

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Bailey, Charles W., Jr. "Electronic (Online) Publishing in Action . . . *The Public-Access Computer Systems Review* and Other Electronic Serials." *ONLINE* 15 (January 1991): 28-35. <http://digital-scholarship.org/cwb/Electronic-Publishing-in-Action.pdf>. Journal ceased publication and is not online. OCLC journal record: <https://ucla.on.worldcat.org/oclc/60630118>.

In June 1989, the University of Houston Libraries established The Public-Access Computer Systems Forum (PACS-L), a LISTSERV-based e-mail discussion list. This list was intended to foster dialog about issues related to the transition from the automation back-room library functions, such as acquisitions, cataloging, and serials control, to a new generation of electronic information systems that could be used directly by patrons. PACS-L covered topics such as the replacement of physical card catalogs with online catalogs, the use of index and abstract CD-ROM workstations, and provision of locally mounted index and abstract databases. In August 1989, University of Houston Libraries launched *The Public-Access Computer Systems Review*, one of the first scholarly e-journals on the Internet. It was freely available, allowed authors to retain their copyrights, had special copyright provisions for noncommercial use, and had a distinguished international editorial team. Issues were announced via e-mail on PACS-L, and articles were distributed as ASCII files from PACS-L's LISTSERV. Since commercial publishers were not even experimenting with electronic journals at this time, this journal, like other early open access journals on the Internet, had to grapple with a number of challenging editorial, format, procedural, policy, and technical issues and, in essence, help invent electronic journal publishing. At this time, the Internet was a collection of imperfectly interconnected independent networks primarily used by academics and other researchers solely for noncommercial purposes and many users of the journal were new to it and its associated technologies, such as e-mail.

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———. "Evolution of an Electronic Book: The *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography*." *The Journal of Electronic Publishing* 7 (December 2001). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0007.201>

The *Scholarly Electronic Publishing Bibliography* (*SEPB*) is an electronic book that currently presents citations for over 1,400 selected English-language articles, books, and other printed and electronic sources that are useful in understanding scholarly electronic publishing efforts on the Internet. Most sources have been published between 1990 and the present; however, a limited number of key sources published prior to 1990 are also included. Where possible, links are provided to sources that are freely available via the Internet. There is no charge for accessing the bibliography.

The first version of the bibliography was published as an article in *The Public-Access Computer Systems Review* (an e-journal) in 1992. It was followed by a part-two article in 1994. These two articles were then used as the basis for a new bibliography article, "Network-Based Electronic Publishing of Scholarly Works: A Selective Bibliography," which was updated 25 times. In 1996, this bibliography was transformed into an electronic book.

SEPB includes "Scholarly Electronic Publishing Resources," a selective directory of related Web sites, and the "Scholarly Electronic Publishing Weblog," a frequently updated list of new publications and other resources that may be of interest to bibliography readers. The bibliography can be searched using Boolean operators.

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INTRODUCTION This paper explores the variability in self-identifying practices of academic libraries engaged in journal publishing and hosting activities. We were interested in how libraries characterized their efforts in this area and looked at whether there is an unspoken threshold for differentiation with respect to publishing-support naming conventions. **METHODS** Using the Library Publishing Directory, in-depth interviews, and a more widely circulated follow-up survey, the research team examined service offerings, divisions of responsibility, funding, terminology, and semantic associations within publishing, both as an active practice and as an advertised service. **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION** We aimed to tease out whether there was any sort of tipping point, or inferred rules, around when an institution chose to call the activity either publishing or hosting. We found no particular service, set of services, funding structure, or division of labor that obviously influenced the use of a particular term. Rather than noting a divide between publishing and hosting, participants spoke of both a spectrum and a tiering of work and support, though all emphasized that these models did not describe the quality of the work produced. This paper also discusses how use of the term library publishing creates additional ambiguity in naming practices, and considers some implications for library staff newly immersed in scholarly publishing work.

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Ayris, Paul. "Open Access E-Books: The Role of the Institution." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 27 (2014): 7-10. <http://doi.org/10.1629/2048-7754.140>

This article explains the policy position taken by University College London (UCL) in establishing the UCL Press. It sets the creation of the Press against the background of national open access (OA) policy development in the UK. UCL Press, repatriated from a commercial provider, was relaunched as an OA press as part of UCL Library Services on 1 August 2013. The Press will publish both OA electronic journals and OA monographs, with a particular emphasis in the latter on the arts, humanities and social sciences. UCL is largely funding Press activity from its own internal funds, seeing OA as an opportunity rather than a threat.

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Ayris, Paul, and Lara Speicher. "UCL Press: the UK's 'First Fully Open Access' University Press." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 28, no. 3 (2015): 44-50. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.257>

The purpose of this article is to set in context the launch of University College London Press (UCL Press), which describes itself as the UK's first fully open access (OA) university press. The drivers for this launch are bound up with the global movement towards open access and open science—developments in which UCL is acknowledged as a European leader. The first part of the article looks at these movements and relates them to the relaunch in May 2015 of the UCL Press imprint as an OA imprint. This analysis has been undertaken by Dr Paul Ayris, Director of UCL Library Services and Chief Executive of UCL Press.

The second half of the article is a personal account by Lara Speicher, Publishing Manager at UCL Press, of the relaunch of the Press. This section looks at staffing structures, business models, technical infrastructures, publishing programmes and content.

In the final part of the article, Paul Ayris draws some conclusions from the history of the relaunch of UCL Press and sets these in the context of the global open science discussion.

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Bailey, D. Russell. "Creating Digital Knowledge: Library as Open Access Digital Publisher." *College & Undergraduate Libraries* 24, no. 2-4 (2017): 216-225. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10691316.2017.1323695>

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Colman, Jason. "Sustainable Book Publishing as a Service at the University of Michigan." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.214>

Only a fairly narrow band of the scholarly output of a university finds a home with commercial publishers or university presses. From niche journals to conference proceedings to technical manuals to monographs with small disciplinary audiences, much of the rest of this work struggles to find a sustainable dissemination strategy. Library publishing operations have stepped into this gap, particularly by offering their services to host small journals and other content based around institutional repositories. This work is often done as inexpensively as possible, with limited, targeted publishing services that just get the job done.

This model tends to break down when a library publisher tries to start doing books. Expectations around design and branding are higher, there is probably no established copyediting process such as a journal run by an external editorial board might already have, and print is often a necessity. It takes a different sort of workflow, and potentially quite a lot more production work, to publish books than it does to publish Open Access journals.

To solve this problem, Michigan Publishing Services has developed both a house service publishing imprint, Maize Books, and a white-labeled book publishing program, branded by University units, all running on the same technical and financial infrastructure. With an emphasis on Open Access with flexible Creative Commons licensing and affordable Print on Demand and EBook options combine workflow efficiencies with a menu of chargeback services to cover the costs of their production and allow staffing to be scaled to meet emerging needs.

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Cox, John. "Communicating New Library Roles to Enable Digital Scholarship: A Review Article." *New Review of Academic Librarianship* 22, no. 2-3 (2016): 132-147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2016.1181665>

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Deville, Joe, Jeroen Sondervan, Graham Stone, and Sofie Wennström. Rebels with a Cause? Supporting Library and Academic-led Open Access Publishing. *LIBER Quarterly* 29, no. 1 (2019): 1–28. <https://liberquarterly.eu/article/view/10733>

The authors, who all have experience with academic publishing, outline the landscape of new university and academic-led open access publishing, before discussing four interrelated sets of challenges which are often referred when questioning the viability of such publishing ventures. They are: (1) professionalism, (2) scale, (3) quality, and (4) discoverability & dissemination. The authors provide examples of how, albeit differing in size, form and ambition, these new presses are not just adhering to conventional publishing norms but often innovating in order to surpass them.

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Dishman, Cath. "Developing an Open Journals Hosting Service: A Case Study from Liverpool John Moores University (LJMU)." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 20, no. 2 (2017): 85-91. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.357>

The rise of the concept of 'library as publisher' has caused many university libraries to consider their role in the world of open access (OA) publishing and how that supports digital scholarship at their institutions. This paper outlines Liverpool John Moores University (LJMU) Library Services' first steps into that world through the offering of an open journals hosting service. It begins by explaining the background and justification for the library offering such a service and details the pilot undertaken to test the chosen system, Open Journal Systems (OJS). It considers what policies, procedures and support need to be in place in order to run a successful open journals hosting service. Lessons learned and observations gathered during the pilot are shared to help others considering setting up an open journals hosting service in their own institution. Finally it looks at the next steps for LJMU in taking this pilot forward to a full service offer.

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Elbae, Mikael K., and Lars Nondal. "The Library as a Mediator for E-Publishing: A Case on How a Library Can Become a Significant Factor in Facilitating Digital Scholarly Communication and Open Access Publishing for Less Web-savvy Journals." *First Monday* 12, no. 10 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v12i10.1958>

Ekanger, Aysa, and Solveig Enoksen. "Support for Good Peer Review in OJS-based Journals: A Library Publisher's Perspective." *Ravnetrykk* 39 (2020): 53–59. <https://doi.org/10.7557/15.5499>

How can a library publishing service with limited resources help editorial teams of peer-reviewed journals in their work? This paper focuses on the technical aspects of the peer review workflow that, if set up and adhered to properly, can contribute to improving the standard of the peer review process—and to some degree also the quality of peer review. The discussion is based on the work done at Septentrio Academic Publishing, the institutional service provider for open access publishing at UiT The Arctic University of Norway.

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Fruin, Christine. "Organization and Delivery of Scholarly Communications Services by Academic and Research Libraries in the United Kingdom: Observations from Across the Pond." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 5, no. 1 (2017): eP2157. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2157>

INTRODUCTION The U.K. library community has implemented collaborative strategies in key scholarly communication areas such as open access mandate compliance, and U.S. librarians could benefit from learning in greater detail about the practices and experiences of U.K. libraries with respect to how they have organized scholarly communication services. **METHODS** In order to better understand the scholarly communication activities in U.K. academic and research libraries, and how U.S. libraries could apply that experience in the context of their own priorities, an environmental scan via a survey of U.K. research libraries and in-person interviews were conducted. **RESULTS** U.K. libraries concentrate their scholarly communication services on supporting compliance with open access mandates and in the development of new services that reflect libraries' shifting role from information consumer to information producer. **DISCUSSION** Due to the difference in the requirements of open access mandates in the U.K. as compared to the U.S., scholarly communication services in the U.K. are more focused on supporting compliance efforts. U.S. libraries engage more actively in providing copyright education and consultation than U.K. libraries. Both U.K. and U.S. libraries have developed new services in the areas of research data management and library publishing. **CONCLUSION** There are three primary takeaways from the experience of U.K. scholarly communication practitioners for U.S. librarians: increase collaboration with offices of research, reconsider current organization and delegation of scholarly communication services, and increase involvement in legislative and policy-making activity in the U.S. with respect to access to research.

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Georgiou, Panos, and Giannis Tsakonas. "Digital Scholarly Publishing and Archiving Services by Academic Libraries: Case Study of the University of Patras." *Liber Quarterly* 20, no. 2 (2010): 242-257. <https://liberquarterly.eu/article/view/10580>

During the last years, dramatic changes in the electronic publishing landscape have created new roles and changed the traditional ones. Presently, some libraries have capitalised on their experience and knowledge in information technology and electronic publishing to undertake such activities, while at the same time they spearhead the campaign for Open Access spreading within academic communities. The Library & Information Centre (LIC) of the University of Patras (UoP), Greece, has been playing an active role in promoting Open Access (OA) in Greece. Since 2007, LIC has been experimenting with OA publishing practices and tools within the framework of various R&D projects. Two of the major results of these efforts are the 'Pasiithe' e-publishing platform and the 'Dexamene' digital archive for Greek scholarly journals. Both platforms are based on OJS—Open Journal Systems e-publishing software. The two facilities were appropriately modified to meet the LIC's publishing and archiving requirements respectively. Currently two journals are being hosted on each platform and all four are from the Humanities. The LIC is negotiating with more publishers and editorial teams to host their journals. In this article we focus on: -technical and managerial key issues of the development and operation phases, -services and procedures, -the business model, -technological, procedural and legal issues and problems that were encountered when working together with publishers, editors and authors, and—future plans for improving and upgrading our e-publishing services into an integrated institutional platform to cover all kinds of publications and data types (monographs, conference proceedings, teaching material, bulletins, magazines etc.). The article concludes with a succinct presentation of the Directory of Greek Digital Resources, a pilot infrastructure developed by the LIC which indexes and presents digital publishing initiatives in Greece and aims to become a formal registry of Greek scholarly resources in digital format.

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Gilman, Isaac. "Adjunct No More: Promoting Scholarly Publishing as a Core Service of Academic Libraries." *Against the Grain* 26, no. 6 (2017): Article 14. <https://doi.org/10.7771/2380-176X.6949>

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Ginther, Clara, Karin Lackner, and Christian Kaier. "Publication Services at the University Library Graz: A New Venture, a New Role." *New Review of Academic Librarianship* 23, no. 2-3 (2017): 136-147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2017.1324802>

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Harboe-Ree, Cathrine. "Just Advanced Librarianship: The Role of Academic Libraries as Publishers." *Australian Academic & Research Libraries* 38, no. 1 (2007): 15-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00048623.2007.10721264>

Hare, Sarah. "Library Publishers as Educators: Crafting Curriculum for Undergraduate Research Journals." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 7, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2296>

INTRODUCTION Library publishing programs continue to play an increasingly important role in educating their constituents. In particular, library publishers that support undergraduate student journals often provide guidance to students on both mechanical and conceptual issues related to publishing. This article presents a case study for developing a one-credit-hour course to support an undergraduate student journal publication, the Indiana University *Journal of Undergraduate Research (IUJUR)*, at Indiana University Bloomington. DESCRIPTION OF COURSE The course is offered every fall as a mechanism for onboarding about thirty new undergraduate editors. The course was developed and taught by a librarian and an undergraduate student in consultation with IU's Office of the Vice Provost for Undergraduate Education. Course curriculum touches on topics that scholarly communication and information literacy librarians alike can adapt for a variety of educational contexts, including authentic activities for understanding peer review models and applying publishing innovations. ASSESSMENT The article details both the formative and summative assessment strategies the instructor utilized to gauge student understanding of key publishing concepts. The summative assessment utilizes pre- and post-tests and extends previous library literature to evaluate students' actual understanding of publishing concepts in addition to their perceived understanding and confidence. LIMITATIONS AND NEXT STEPS The course curriculum will continue to grow and change in order to accommodate students' misconceptions and interests.

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Harley, Diane, ed. *The University as Publisher: Summary of a Meeting Held at UC Berkeley on November 1, 2007*. Berkeley: Center for Studies in Higher Education, 2008. <https://web.archive.org/web/20210120233636/https://cshe.berkeley.edu/publications/university-publisher-summary-meeting-held-uc-berkeley-november-1-2007>

Hawkins, Kevin S. "Achieving Financial Sustainability: Are We Asking the Wrong Questions?" *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.213>

While technology has made producing copies of digital content almost entirely free, there is no escaping that publishing, according to most definitions of the term, still requires time and money. Any publishing service offered by a library must find a way to achieve financial sustainability—that is, operate without losing money.

However, even "losing money" is a tricky concept, especially when taking into account varying definitions of operating expenses (overhead costs) under different models for auxiliary services. Libraries are by their very nature cost centers, providing services without the expectation of recovering revenue, and are usually part of larger organizations that similarly provide services under partial or full subsidies. While libraries are often comfortable with charging for convenience services and for services to those outside their designed community of users, careful thought should be given to which costs a publishing service—or any new service—should be expected to recover.

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———. "Creating a Library Publishing Program for Scholarly Books: Your Options Are Limited." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 7, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2262>

Publishing programs in academic libraries vary in their scope, offerings, and business models. Despite the many forms that these programs take, I have argued in the past that various factors constrain the design of a start-up publishing operation. In this commentary, I discuss in greater depth the key questions to be addressed before establishing a library publishing program for scholarly books, arguing that the viable options are in fact quite limited.

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———. "The Evolution of Publishing Agreements at the University of Michigan Library." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1175. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1175>

Taking as an example an open-access journal with a single editor, this article discusses the various configurations of rights agreements used by the University of Michigan Library throughout the evolution of its

publishing operation, the advantages of the various models, and the reasons for moving from one to another.

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Henry, Charles. "Rice University Press: Fons et Origo." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 10, no. 2 (2007). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0010.205>

Ho, Adrian K. "Creating and Hosting Student-Run Research Journals: A Case Study." *Partnership: The Canadian Journal of Library and Information Practice and Research* 6, no. 2 (2011). <https://journal.lib.uoguelph.ca/index.php/perj/article/view/1516>

Hollister, Christopher V., Karen Bjork, and Stewart Brower. "A Multi-Institutional Model for Advancing Open Access Journals and Reclaiming Control of the Scholarly Record." *Serials Librarian* 80, no. 1-4 (2021): 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2021.1863141>

Hoops, Jenny, and Sarah Hare. "Library Publisher Resources: Making Publishing Approachable, Sustainable, and Values-Driven." *College & Research Libraries News* 80, no. 2 (2019): 74-77. <https://doi.org/10.5860/CRLN.80.2.74>

Johnston, Chelsea, and Jason Boczar. "Scholarly Publishing Literacy at the University of South Florida Libraries: From Advising to Active Involvement." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 7, no. 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2310>

INTRODUCTION Successful open access (OA) publishing in libraries requires careful guidance and organization. Support and services offered vary depending on available resources as well as the robustness of a library's publishing program. DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM This article describes the connection between publishing services and scholarly publishing literacy through examples from the University of South Florida (USF) Libraries. The USF Libraries' OA publishing program includes journals, textbooks, conference proceedings, and more. Our program balances advocating for open access with advising for actions that serve our partners' goals. This invites trust, sustainable relationships, and opportunities for new work. NEXT STEPS At the USF Libraries, more work must be done to formally assess our efforts. Our program will also explore new ways to support the ethical standards expected of libraries by pursuing stronger policies on diversity and inclusion. Using everyday work to demonstrate best practices is a manageable way to strengthen scholarly publishing efforts. We hope to continue growing our services, empowering our partners, and exploring our roles as advisors and advocates.

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Kate, Lara. "The Library's Role in the Management and Funding of Open Access Publishing." *Learned Publishing* 28, no. 1 (2015): 4-8. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20150102>

Keller, Alice. "Library Support for Open Access Journal Publishing: A Needs Analysis." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 28, no. 3 (2015): 19-31. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.256>

The aim of this study was to establish the role of academic libraries in the context of open access (OA) journal publishing, based on the perceived needs of the journals and/or their editors. As a study sample, 14 OA journals affiliated to the University of Zürich, Switzerland, were taken. They were very different in nature, ranging from well-established society journals to newly founded titles launched by dedicated individuals. The study comprised two approaches: a comprehensive journal assessment and subsequent editor interviews. The journal assessments evaluated the functionalities, ease of use, sustainability and visibility of the journal. The interviews were used to get additional background information about the journals and explore editors' needs, experiences and viewpoints. The results show that journals affiliated to publishing houses or libraries are technically well provided for. Unaffiliated journals offer fewer functionalities and display some unconventional features, often described as innovations by the editors. More resources—financial or human—is seen by nearly all editors as the most pressing need and as a limitation to growth. In comparison, IT/technical needs are mentioned much less often. The article also describes the launch of an Editors' Forum, an idea suggested by the editors and implemented by the library. This Forum offered further valuable insight into the potential role of libraries, but also specifically addressed several of the editors' needs as expressed in the interviews.

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Kolesnykova, Tetiana, and Olena Matveyeva. "An Analysis of Digital Library Publishing Services in Ukrainian Universities." *Evidence Based Library and Information Practice* 14, no. 4 (2019): 52-71. <https://doi.org/10.18438/ebliip29510>

Kosavic, Andrea. "The York Digital Journals Project: Strategies for Institutional Open Journal Systems Implementations." *College & Research Libraries* 71, no. 4 (2010): 310-321. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl-36r1>

Koskinen, Kimmo, Markku Roinila, and Kati Pauliina Syvälahti. "Open Journal Systems as a Pedagogical Tool to Teach and Learn Scholarly Publishing: The Helsinki University Library Experience." *LIBER Quarterly* 31, no. 1 (2021): 1–17. <https://liberquarterly.eu/article/view/10881>

Academic libraries play a pivotal role in promoting open science, providing essential services for opening research and education. The library has also a key role in increasing awareness of open educational resources and practices. Editori is an open journal service at the University of Helsinki designed with an educational focus,

providing simultaneously a contribution to the rising trend of university-based and library-based publishing. We show how this service, based on Open Journal Systems (OJS), can be applied as a pedagogical tool for teaching scholarly publishing skills to university students. In 2019 Helsinki University Library initiated a pilot project together with the Working Seminar of Doctoral Programme in Philosophy, Arts and Society of the Arts Faculty of the University of Helsinki. We outline expected pedagogical outcomes from the project, relating to scholarly communication skills, report feedback from teachers and students and discuss implications for future service development. In sum, students and teachers found the Editori platform intuitive and easy to use, although the learning curve for course leaders was considered steep in the initial phase.

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Lawson, Stuart. "Library Publishing Services: An Investigation into Open Access Publishing in Academic Libraries." University of Brighton, 2013. <http://eprints.rclis.org/25156/>

Lawrence, Janna C. "Libraries as Journal Publishers." *Journal of Electronic Resources in Medical Libraries* 7, no. 3 (2010): 235-240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15424065.2010.505516>

Lefevre, Julie, and Terence K. Huwe. "Digital Publishing from the Library: A New Core Competency." *Journal of Web Librarianship* 7, no. 2 (2013): 190-214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19322909.2013.780519>

Library Publishing Coalition Directory Committee. *Library Publishing Directory 2021*. Atlanta, GA: Library Publishing Coalition, 2021. https://librarypublishing.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/library_publishing_directory_2021_Web.pdf

The eighth edition of the *Library Publishing Directory* provides a snapshot of the publishing activities of over 150 academic and research libraries, including information about the number and types of publications they produce, the services they offer authors, how they are staffed and funded, and their future plans. In documenting the breadth and depth of activities in this field, this resource aims to articulate the unique value of library publishing; to establish it as a significant and growing community of practice; and to raise its visibility within a number of stakeholder communities, including administrators, funding agencies, other scholarly publishers, librarians, and content creators.

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Library Publishing Coalition Ethical Framework Task Force. *An Ethical Framework for Library Publishing, Version 1.0*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia, 2018. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5703/1288284316777>.

Library publishing is distinguished in part from other types of scholarly publishing by a focus on adherence to the values and ethics of librarianship. *An Ethical Framework for Library Publishing* supports good practice in this area by providing resources and guidance in a number of ethical areas of importance to library publishers. Version 1.0 (published July 2018) covers publishing practice; accessibility; diversity, equity, and inclusion; privacy and analytics; and academic and intellectual freedom.

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Library Publishing Coalition Professional Development Committee. *Library Publishing Competencies*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia Institute, 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5703/1288284317123>

This publication provides a list of skills and knowledge useful in the development and provision of publishing services in libraries, organized into three categories: publishing, program development and management, and teaching and consulting. It will support publishing programs in identifying essential skills and will help individuals in the field to identify their strengths and the areas in which they are interested in growing. Published April 2020.

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Library Publishing Coalition Professional Development Committee. *Library Publishing Documentation Toolkit*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia Institute, 2021. https://librarypublishing.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/LPC_DocumentationToolkit2021_FINAL.pdf

The toolkit is organized in four sections. The first two sections, Getting Started with Documentation and Planning a Documentation Day, focus on preparing and creating a plan for your Documentation Day. The third section, Suggested Documentation Projects to Tackle, provides some ideas for the kinds of projects you can work on, broken down by scope (one person, small group, big picture). The final section, Sharing Documentation Beyond Your Institution, includes some things to consider to help you determine when/if you should share your documentation. It also provides information on sharing through the Library Publishing Coalition Shared Documentation Portal.

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Library Publishing Coalition Research Committee. *Library Publishing Research Agenda*. Atlanta, GA: Educopia Institute, 2020. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5703/1288284317124>

This publication is an exploration of areas in which research is needed to support practice in the field of library publishing. The Research Agenda offers exploratory overviews of six topics (assessment, labor, accessibility, non-traditional research outputs, peer review, and partnerships), each of which includes a summary, potential

research questions, and a list of relevant resources. This publication will be of interest to anyone conducting or interested in conducting research in the field.

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Lippincott, Sarah Kalikman. "The Library Publishing Coalition: Organizing Libraries to Enhance Scholarly Publishing." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 29, no. 2 (2016): 186-191. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.296>

Library-based publishing efforts are gaining traction in academic and research libraries across the world, primarily in response to perceived gaps in the scholarly publishing system. Though publishing is a new area of work for libraries, it is often a natural outgrowth of their existing infrastructure and skill sets, leveraging the institutional repository as publishing platform and repositioning librarians' skills as information managers. For decades, these initiatives were primarily ad hoc and local, limiting the potential for library publishing to effect significant change. In 2013, over 60 academic and research libraries collectively founded the Library Publishing Coalition (LPC), a professional association expressly charged with facilitating knowledge sharing, collaboration and advocacy for this growing field. This article offers an overview of library publishing activity, primarily in the US, followed by an account of the creation and mission of the LPC, the first professional association dedicated wholly to the support of library publishers.

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Little, Geoffrey Robert. "Nothing New Under the Sun: Library Publishing and the Concordia University." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.205>

The author of Ecclesiastes tells us that there is nothing new under the sun.[1] In their excellent 2015 report *The Once and Future Publishing Library*, Ann Okerson and Alex Holzman remind readers that library publishing has a venerable history. Indeed, many of the oldest North American university presses like those at Johns Hopkins, North Carolina, and Toronto were set up by librarians or based in the university library system.[2] Since 2013 we have been working on a project at Concordia University in Montreal to establish a university press that will be based in our library and that will publish peer-reviewed monographs in the humanities, social sciences, and fine arts. Digital editions will be available open access under a creative commons licence, while print books will be simultaneously published where and when appropriate and available for purchase by individual readers and libraries. Authors will be published irrespective of their institutional affiliation. This paper is a brief description of our project that includes an overview of our processes and planning, lessons learned, and next steps in the short and long terms.

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———. "Old Traditions and New Technologies: Creating Concordia University Press." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 49, no. 2 (2018): 213-230. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.49.2.213>

Loizides, Fernando. "Sustaining the Growth of Library Scholarly Publishing in a New University Press." *Information Services & Use* 36, no. 3-4 (2016): 147-158. <https://content.iospress.com/articles/information-services-and-use/isu812>

McCready, Kate, and Emma Molls. "Developing a Business Plan for a Library Publishing Program." *Publications* 6, no. 4 (2018): 42. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PUBLICATIONS6040042>

Over the last twenty years, library publishing has emerged in higher education as a new class of publisher. Conceived as a response to commercial publishing practices that have strained library budgets and prevented scholars from openly licensing and sharing their works, library publishing is both a local service program and a broader movement to disrupt the current scholarly publishing arena. It is growing both in numbers of publishers and numbers of works produced. The commercial publishing framework which determines the viability of monetizing a product is not necessarily applicable for library publishers who exist as a common good to address the needs of their academic communities. Like any business venture, however, library publishers must develop a clear service model and business plan in order to create shared expectations for funding streams, quality markers, as well as technical and staff capacity. As the field is maturing from experimental projects to full programs, library publishers are formalizing their offerings and limitations. The anatomy of a library publishing business plan is presented and includes the principles of the program, scope of services, and staffing requirements. Other aspects include production policies, financial structures, and measures of success.

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McIntyre, Gordon, Janice Chan, and Julia Gross. "Library as Scholarly Publishing Partner: Keys to Success." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 1 (2013): eP1091. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1091>

Many academic libraries are looking at new ways to add value when they deliver services to faculty, and one potential area where the library can provide new services is in partnering with academic staff to support the dissemination of faculty research. Librarians have traditionally helped faculty researchers at the beginning of the research cycle, with the discovery and delivery of information sources. However, they are now playing a role at the end of the research cycle, providing services that support scholarly publishing. This paper examines library participation in faculty-led publishing ventures. In particular, it explores the value that smaller research libraries can provide to faculty editors through journal hosting, which will be analysed through an examination of the successful migration of the *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, a faculty-administered journal at Edith

Cowan University in Perth, Western Australia, to the University's institutional repository. This transition provided library staff members at Edith Cowan University opportunities to develop new knowledge and skills in journal publishing, while meeting the journal's need for a better way to manage a growing influx of article submissions. The resultant faculty-library partnership enabled more effective management of the journal and has contributed to its growing success. The evaluative framework developed to enable assessment of the success of this journal's transition can help other libraries demonstrate the success of their own journal hosting ventures.

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McMahon, Melody Layton. "The Library as Publisher? Is It Possible for a Small Library?" *Theological Librarianship* 8, no. 1 (2015): 4-6. <https://doi.org/10.31046/tl.v8i1.365>

Missingham, Roxanne, and Lorena Kanellopoulos. "University Presses in Libraries: Potential for Successful Marriages." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 30, no. 3 (2014): 158-166. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-01-2014-0001>

Molls, Emma J. "Assessing the Success of Library Published Journals." *Against the Grain* 31, no. 4 (2019): Article 13. <https://doi.org/10.7771/2380-176X.8414>

Moody, Fred. "Rice University Press: Nascent Fame." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 16, no. 1 (2013). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0016.102>

Rice University Press (RUP), which began full operation in February 2007, proved a short-lived experiment. After three years of supporting one paid staff position and modest additional funding for contracted book design work, office expenses, and travel,[1] Rice closed the press down as part of a larger, campuswide, budget-cutting effort. Faced with a choice between investing more financial and human capital in its press as a condition for gaining substantial foundation support or opting out of the experiment altogether, university administration chose the latter.

Short-lived as the RUP experience was, it nevertheless offers some important lessons for people pondering the future of academic publishing and its inexorable move in a digital direction. There is no question that traditional printed-on-paper publishing is dying out and that it will be replaced by digital academic discourse distributed on a different economic model. There are, however, substantial questions about when and how this paradigm shift will come about, and the Rice University Press story may offer some answers.

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Moulaison, Heather Lea, and Anthony J. Million. "E-Publishing in Libraries: The [Digital] Preservation Imperative." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 2 (2015): 87-98. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-02-2014-0009>

Mullins, James L., Catherine Murray-Rust, Joyce L. Ogburn, Raym Crow, October Ivins, Allyson Mower, Daureen Nesdill, Mark Newton, Julie Speer, and Charles Watkinson. *Library Publishing Services: Strategies for Success: Final Research Report*. Washington, DC: SPARC, 2012. <https://libres.uncg.edu/ir/listing.aspx?id=17801>

Nelson, Rebecca, and Becky Thoms. "The Practical and the Aspirational: Managing the Student Employee Experience in Library Publishing Efforts." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 9, no. 1 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.31274/jlsc.12913>

Student employees are a critical component in the workforce of academic libraries. While more established library services have the benefit of attracting student employees specifically interested in their work, scholarly communication programs, and library publishing efforts in particular, have more difficulty describing and garnering interest in their work. This article describes the journey of the Digital Initiatives Unit at Utah State University Libraries as we navigated the particular trials that come with library publishing—specifically delving into the work of our institutional repository (IR) and the role of student employees in those efforts. The labor of our program is variable and largely project-based, which has presented a number of challenges related to our student employees: understanding the larger context of their work; retention of knowledge and skills alongside their ability to prioritize; and a struggle to transfer skills from one project to another. Addressing these problems involved more intentional gathering of student feedback, colleague brainstorming, and trial and error; through which process and results we are gaining a more developed understanding of the critical importance of the student experience. When student employees see their work as more than just a job, and recognize the skills they are learning, they come away with greater satisfaction and our unit benefits from improved outputs. Using what we have learned, we will be able to continue our efforts for a better student experience as well as creating future goals for our unit.

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Ogburn, Joyce. *Library Publishing Services: Strategies for Success: Final Research Report*. 2015. https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/purduepress_ebooks/24/

Okerson, Ann, and Alex Holzman. *The Once and Future Publishing Library*. Washington, DC: CLIR, 2015. <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub166/>

Park, Ji-Hong, and Jiyoun Shim. "Exploring How Library Publishing Services Facilitate Scholarly Communication." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 43, no. 1 (2011): 76-89. <https://doi.org/10.1353/scp.2011.0038>

Perry, Anali Maughan, Carol Ann Borchert, Timothy S. Deliyannides, Andrea Kosavic, Rebecca Kennison, and Sharon Dyas-Correia. "Libraries as Journal Publishers." *Serials Review* 37, no. 3 (2011): 196-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2011.10765382>

Pitcher, Kate. "Library Publishing of Open Textbooks: The Open SUNY Textbooks Program." *Against the Grain* 26, no. 5 (2014): Article 10. <https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/atg/vol26/iss5/10/>

Raju, Reggie, Jill Claassen, and Lena Nyahodza. "Library Publishing for an Inclusive Education." *Humanizing LIS Education and Practice* (2020): 145–57. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429356209-12>

Raju, Reggie, Jill Claassen, Jeremiah Pietersen, and Danielle Abrahamse. "An Authentic Flip Subscription Model for Africa: Library as Publisher Service." *Library Management* 41, no. 6/7 (2020): 369-381. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-03-2020-0054>

Raju, Reggie, and Jeremiah Pietersen. "Library as Publisher: From an African Lens." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.203>

Africa is trapped in two paradoxical situations. The first is that the production of research is dependent on access to research—African researchers have been hamstrung by limited access to relevant and authentic scholarly literature to support the growth in their research output. It has been mooted that the saviour is improved access to open content. This gives rise to the second paradox—open access removes the financial barriers to the end user. In this new paradigm, the cash-cow for publishers is now the author via the payment of article processing charges (APCs). However, African researchers, in the main, cannot afford these exorbitant APCs, limiting their capacity to publish excellent research in leading international journals that have an OA publishing option.

Hence, it is incumbent on research intensive institutions on the African continent to take the lead in sharing scholarly output to engender and nurture a culture of research at those African institutions that are overwhelmed by low research output. To support the dissemination of trusted and relevant scholarly content, African libraries need to provide proactive 'library as publisher' services. These services must be delivered for non-profit purposes and must be underpinned by 'philanthropic-social justice' principles.

Some South African academic institutions, via their libraries, have stepped-up to the plate to make scholarly freely content accessible to both users and authors via suite of diamond open access services. The library as a publisher must gain traction quickly as a mainstream service provided by the higher education libraries in South Africa.

This paper will examine the new trend of library as a publisher from a developing world perspective. The benefits for the provision of 'library as publisher' service is colossal for development in the global South.

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Rayner, Sarah, and Desmond Coyle. "Books Right Here Right Now at the University of Manchester Library." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 29, no. 2 (2016): 172-180. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.309>

Books Right Here Right Now is a strategic project to radically change core text provision at the University of Manchester. In order to investigate new models for electronic textbook delivery, the project team are running a series of e-textbook pilots, providing textbooks directly to our students via the virtual learning environment.

This paper focuses on how usage data and the views of our students and academic staff are underpinning the project in terms of acquisition models, negotiations with publishers and providing a new product to our students. Having detailed the project findings, the article concludes with the authors' thoughts on the changing environment of the e-textbook market and the various issues within the existing models of e-textbook provision, giving recommendations as to how academic libraries and publishers can help to shape a sustainable model for the UK.

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Richard, Jennifer, Denise Koufogiannakis, and Pam Ryan. "Librarians and Libraries Supporting Open Access Publishing." *Canadian Journal of Higher Education* 39, no. 3 (2009): 33-48. <http://journals.sfu.ca/cjhe/index.php/cjhe/article/view/474>

Riddle, Kelly. "Creating Policies for Library Publishing in an Institutional Repository: Exploring Purpose, Scope, and the Library's Role." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 2 (2015): 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-02-2014-0007>

Robertson, Wendy C., and Charlene N. Simser. "Managing E-Publishing: Perfect Harmony for Serialists." *Serials Librarian* 64, no. 1-4 (2013): 118–128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361526X.2013.760399>

Roh, Charlotte. "Library Publishing and Diversity Values: Changing Scholarly Publishing through Policy and Scholarly Communication Education." *College & Research Libraries News*, 77, no. 2 (2016): 82–85. <https://doi.org/10.5860/CRLN.77.2.9446>

Roh, Charlotte, and Vanessa Gabler. "Systemic Barriers and Allyship in Library Publishing: A Case Study Reminder That No One Is Safe from Racism." *College & Research Libraries News* 81, no. 3 (2020): 141–144. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.81.3.141>

Royster, Paul. "Library Publishing Is Special: Selection and Eligibility in Library Publishing." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): p.eP1183. <https://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1183>

Traditional publishing is based on ownership, commerce, paid exchanges, and scholarship as a commodity, while library activities are based on a service model of sharing resources and free exchange. I believe library publishing should be based on those values and should not duplicate or emulate traditional publishing. University presses have mixed views of library publishing, and libraries should not adopt those attitudes. Library publishers are not gatekeepers; their mission is dissemination. Libraries need to publish because traditional publishing suffers from high rejection rates, required surrender of intellectual property, long production schedules, high cost of products, and limited dissemination. Nebraska's Zea Books is a response to these needs. Miscellaneous advice for library publishers is offered and selection and eligibility criteria are outlined. A suggestion is made for a cooperative ebook distribution network.

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Sandy, Heather Moulaison, and Janice Bially Mattern. "Academic Library-Based Publishing: A State of the Evolving Art." *Library Trends* 67, no. 2 (2018): 337–357. <https://doi.org/10.1353/LIB.2018.0040>

Santiago, Ariana, and Lauren Ray. "Navigating Support Models for OER Publishing: Case Studies from the University of Houston and the University of Washington." *Reference Services Review* 48, no. 3 (2020): 397-413. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RSR-03-2020-0019>

Saunders, Richard L. "Where Do We Go From Here? Starting Up an Academic Journal In a Smaller Institution." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 2 (2017). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.209>

There is no reliable formula for starting or sustaining a scholarly journal. This essay encourages readers to develop and address sustainable editorial and publication processes, addressing five key elements that increase the likelihood that a journal can be successfully sustained over time. . . .

This essay illustrates decisions and opportunities which need definition when establishing and disseminating a viable scholarly journal. Each concern and issue should be considered and resolved; each decision will lead to other decisions as academic institutions once again transcend being merely warehouses for knowledge and become again disseminators of it. The comments here are drawn from lessons learned over several years working in the publishing industry and as an author myself. It is not a how-to guide, nor does it guarantee success. The observations are prompts intended to help librarians as would-be publishers think carefully. The goal for this article is not to encourage library publishing per se, but rather to help readers understand the moving parts involved in establishing a flexible, resilient process that can sustain a publication in the long term and independent of the personalities driving its creation. I presume that libraries will be required to start small and bootstrap their journals into existence, for the sort of investment capital start-up common to the tech and software industries is typically lacking in academia. I also presume that institutions will craft a scholarly journal rather than a trade journal or non-specialist magazine. Comments are grouped into five broad sections or processes for convenience. Key points are rendered in italics for convenience and clarity within paragraphs.

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Schlosser, Melanie. "Building Capacity for Academy-Owned Publishing through the Library Publishing Coalition." *Library Trends* 67, no. 2 (2018): 359–375. <https://doi.org/10.1353/LIB.2018.0041>

———. "Write up! A Study of Copyright Information on Library-Published Journals." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 4 (2016). <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.2110>

INTRODUCTION Libraries have a mission to educate users about copyright, and library publishing staff are often involved in that work. This article investigates a concrete point of intersection between the two areas—copyright statements on library-published journals. **METHODS** Journals published by members of the Library Publishing Coalition were examined for open access status, type and placement of copyright information, copyright ownership, and open licensing. **RESULTS** Journals in the sample were overwhelmingly (93%) open access. 80% presented copyright information of some kind, but only 30% of those included it at both the journal and the article level. Open licensing was present in 38% of the journals, and the most common ownership scenario was the author retaining copyright while granting a nonexclusive license to the journal or publisher. 9% of the sample journals included two or more conflicting rights statements. **DISCUSSION** 76% of the journals did not consistently provide accurate, easily-accessible rights information, and numerous problems were found with the use of open licensing, including conflicting licenses, incomplete licenses, and licenses not appearing at the article level. **CONCLUSION** Recommendations include presenting full copyright and licensing information at both the journal and the article level, careful use of open licenses, and publicly-available author agreements.

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Shuttleworth, Kate, Kevin Stranack, and Alison Moore. "Course Journals: Leveraging Library Publishing to Engage Students at the Intersection of Open Pedagogy, Scholarly Communications, and Information Literacy." *Partnership: The Canadian Journal of Library and Information Practice and Research*. 14, no. 2 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.21083/partnership.v14i2.5339>

Skinner, Katherine, Sarah Lippincott, Julie Speer, and Tyler Walters. "Library-as-Publisher: Capacity Building for the Library Publishing Subfield." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 17, no. 2 (2014). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0017.207>

Skinner, Katherine, Melanie Schlosser, Peter Berkery, Meredith Baab, Jasmine Mulliken, Friederike Sundaram, Dennis Lloyd, Mary Rose Muccie, Brenna McLaughlin, and John W. Warren. "Library Publishing Curriculum Textbook." *Library Publishing Curriculum 1* (2021): Article 30.

<https://digitalcommons.wayne.edu/libpubcurriculum/vol1/iss1/30>

In the original, modular curriculum (2018) on which this textbook is based, each unit of the Library Publishing Curriculum contained an instructor's guide, narrative, a slideshow with talking notes, bibliographies, supplemental material, and activities for use in a physical or virtual classroom for workshops and courses. This textbook version, produced in 2021, adapts the original narrative as the primary content (with very little additional editing) and incorporates the bibliographies, appendices, and images from the slideshow into a linear reading and learning experience for use by librarians or students learning on their own or as part of a classroom learning experience. The LPC hopes others use and extend this CC-BY version into even more learning opportunities to help create a more equitable publishing ecosystem.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Sondervan, Jeroen, and Fleur Stigter. "Sustainable Open Access for Scholarly Journals in 6 Years —The Incubator Model at Utrecht University Library Open Access Journals." *Learned Publishing* 31, no. 3 (2018): 230-234. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1151>

Stockham, Marcia G., Elizabeth Turtle, and Charlene N. Simser. "Libraries as Publishers: A Winning Combination." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 2 (2015): 69-75. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-01-2014-0006>

Stone, Graham. "Huddersfield Open Access Publishing." *Information Services & Use* 31, no. 3-4 (2011): 215-223. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3233/ISU-2012-0651>

Stone, Graham, Kathrine Jensen, and Megan Beech. "Publishing Undergraduate Research: Linking Teaching and Research through a Dedicated Peer-Reviewed Open Access Journal." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 47, no. 2 (2016): 147-170. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jsp.47.2.147>

Stranack, Kevin. "Sustaining Library Publishing Through Multi-Stakeholder Cooperatives." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 20, no. 2 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0020.216>

Library-based open access publishing continues to grow internationally, with a variety of economic models emerging to provide sustainable funding for the production and dissemination of high quality, peer-reviewed publications. Although author processing charges have become increasingly common, some library-based publishers are experimenting with cooperative structures where key stakeholders, including libraries, societies, funding agencies, and others come together to collectively fund and support publishing activities. This session will report on the MacArthur-funded Open Access Publishing Cooperative Study, which is investigating the viability of publishing cooperatives through an examination of pilot projects from around the world.

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Taylor, Megan, and Kathrine S. H. Jensen. "Engaging and Supporting a University Press Scholarly Community." *Publications* 6, no. 2 (2018): 13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/publications6020013>

In this paper we explore how the development of The University of Huddersfield Press, a publisher of open access scholarly journals and monographs, has enabled the sharing of research with a wider online audience. We situate the development of the Press within a wider research environment and growing community of New University Presses (NUPs) where there is an increasing demand for demonstrating research impact, which drives the need for improved analysis and reporting of impact data, a task that often falls within the remit of library and academic support services. We detail the benefits of the University Press Manager role in terms of ensuring professional service that delivers consistency and sustainability. We go on to outline the experiences of engaging with different online spaces and detail the extensive support for student authors. We argue that in order for the Press to support building a strong and engaged scholarly community and provide new spaces for emerging research, continued investment in both platform development and infrastructure is required.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Thomas, Sarah E. "Publishing Solutions for Contemporary Scholars: The Library as Innovator and Partner." *Publishing Research Quarterly* 22, no. 2 (2006): 27-37. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12109-006-0013-5>

Tracy, Daniel G. "Libraries as Content Producers: How Library Publishing Services Address the Reading Experience." *College & Research Libraries* 78, no. 2 (2017): 219-240. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.78.2.16583>

———. "The Users of Library Publishing Services: Readers and Access Beyond Open." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 18, no. 3 (2015). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0018.303>

Unsworth, John M. "Pubrarians and Liblishers at 20: Reflections on Library Publishing from 1995-2014." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1201. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1201>

Vandegrift, Micah, and Josh Bolick. "'Free to All': Library Publishing and the Challenge of Open Access." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 2, no. 4 (2014): eP1181. <http://doi.org/10.7710/2162-3309.1181>

There is a significant and important responsibility as libraries move into the role of publishing to retain our heritage of "access for all." Connecting and collaborating with colleagues in the publishing industry is essential, but should come with the understanding that the library as an organization is access-prone. This article discusses the complexities of navigating that relationship, and calls for libraries and publishers to embrace and respect the position from which we begin. Finally, the article forecasts several possible characteristics of what "publishing" might look like if libraries press the principle of access in this growing area.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Walters, Tyler. "The Future Role of Publishing Services in University Libraries Initiatives." *portal: Libraries and the Academy* 8, no. 4 (2008): 425-454. <https://doi.org/10.1353/scp.2011.0035>

Watkinson, Charles. "The University as Publisher Revisited." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 27, no. 2 (2014): 181-185. <http://doi.org/10.1629/2048-7754.131>

This article explores the growing involvement of libraries in providing publishing services for the informal scholarly outputs traditionally referred to as 'gray literature'. By envisioning institutional repository (IR) infrastructure as a publishing platform, libraries can bring conference proceedings, technical reports, niche journals, white papers and other hard-to-source materials into the mainstream. The opportunities of such an approach for scholars, libraries and university presses open to collaboration are considered. Several directions for future expansion of this activity, such as the publication of student scholarship and the development of more formal products linked to gray literature, are suggested.

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Wipperman, Sarah L., Shawn Martin, and Chealsye Bowley. "Balancing Influence in a Shifting Scholarly Communication Landscape: Creating Library-Owned, Community-Aligned Infrastructure through Individual, Local, and Community Action." *College & Research Libraries News* 79, no. 5 (2018): 244-247. <https://doi.org/10.5860/CRLN.79.5.244>

Xia, Jingfeng. "Library Publishing as a New Model of Scholarly Communication." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 40, no. 4 (2009): 370-338. <https://doi.org/10.1353/scp.0.0052>

4.0 Technical Publishing Infrastructure

Altman, Micah, Eleni Castro, Mercè Crosas, Philip Durbin, Alex Garnett, and Jen Whitney. "Open Journal Systems and Dataverse Integration—Helping Journals to Upgrade Data Publication for Reusable Research." *Code4Lib Journal*, no. 30 (2015). <https://journal.code4lib.org/articles/10989>

This article describes the novel open source tools for open data publication in open access journal workflows. This comprises a plugin for Open Journal Systems that supports a data submission, citation, review, and publication workflow; and an extension to the Dataverse system that provides a standard deposit API. We describe the function and design of these tools, provide examples of their use, and summarize their initial reception. We conclude by discussing future plans and potential impact.

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Bankier, Jean-Gabriel, and Irene Perciali. "The Institutional Repository Rediscovered: What Can a University Do for Open Access Publishing?" *Serials Review* 34, no. 1 (2008): 21-26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2008.10765147>

Bernhardt, Beth R. "Library Roles in Supporting Creation of Serials: Open Journal Systems at The University of North Carolina at Greensboro." *Serials Review* 42, no. 3 (2016): 240-242. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2016.1204204>

Bertino, Andrea C., and Heather Staines. "Enabling A Conversation Across Scholarly Monographs through Open Annotation." *Publications* 7, no. 2 (2019): 41. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PUBLICATIONS7020041>

The digital format opens up new possibilities for interaction with monographic publications. In particular, annotation tools make it possible to broaden the discussion on the content of a book, to suggest new ideas, to report errors or inaccuracies, and to conduct open peer reviews. However, this requires the support of the users who might not yet be familiar with the annotation of digital documents. This paper will give concrete examples and recommendations for exploiting the potential of annotation in academic research and teaching. After presenting the annotation tool of Hypothesis, the article focuses on its use in the context of HIRMEOS (High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science Infrastructure), a project aimed to improve the Open Access digital monograph. The general line and the aims of a post-peer review experiment with the annotation tool, as well as its usage in didactic activities concerning monographic publications are presented and proposed as potential best practices for similar annotation activities

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Büttner, Alexandra, Sabine Gehrlein, and Stefanie Clormann. "Online Survey on Open Journal Systems in Germany and the Network OJS-de.net." *Scholarly and Research Communication* 7, no. 1 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.22230/src.2016v7n1a240>

Castro, Eleni, and Alex Garnett. "Building a Bridge Between Journal Articles and Research Data: The PKP-Dataverse Integration Project." *International Journal of Digital Curation* 9, no. 1 (2014): 176-184. <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v9i1.311>

A growing number of funding agencies and international scholarly organizations are requesting that research data be made more openly available to help validate and advance scientific research. Thus, this is an opportune moment for research data repositories to partner with journal editors and publishers in order to simplify and improve data curation and publishing practices. One practical example of this type of cooperation is currently being facilitated by a two year (2012-2014) one million dollar Sloan Foundation grant, integrating two well-established open source systems: the Public Knowledge Project's (PKP) Open Journal Systems (OJS), developed by Stanford University and Simon Fraser University; and Harvard University's Dataverse Network web application, developed by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS). To help make this interoperability possible, an OJS Dataverse plugin and Data Deposit API are being developed, which together will allow authors to submit their articles and datasets through an existing journal management interface, while the underlying data are seamlessly deposited into a research data repository, such as the Harvard Dataverse. This practice paper will provide an overview of the project, and a brief exploration of some of the specific challenges to and advantages of this integration.

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Czyzyk, Mark, and Sayeed Choudhury. "A Survey and Evaluation of Open-Source Electronic Publishing Systems." (2008). <http://jhir.library.jhu.edu/handle/1774.2/32737>

Daly, Rebecca, and Michael Organ. "Research Online: Digital Commons as a Publishing Platform at the University of Wollongong, Australia." *Serials Review* 35, no. 3 (2009): 149-153. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2009.10765233>

Edgar, Brian D., and John Willinsky. "A Survey of Scholarly Journals Using Open Journal Systems." *Scholarly and Research Communication* 1, no. 2 (2010): 020105. <https://src-online.ca/index.php/src/article/view/24/41>

Elizarov, A. M., D. S. Zuev, and E. K. Lipachev. "Electronic Scientific Journal-Management Systems." *Scientific and Technical Information Processing* 41, no. 1 (2014): 66-72. <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0147688214010109>

Eve, Martin Paul, and Andy Byers. "Janeway: A Scholarly Communications Platform." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 31, no. 15 (2018). <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.396>

Bearing these considerations in mind, the Centre for Technology and Publishing at Birkbeck, University of London embarked upon building a journal submission and hosting platform, Janeway, learning from our experiences of running the Open Library of Humanities (OLH). We knew Open Journal Systems (OJS) well at this time, but were not big fans of PHP, the language in which it is written. We also were aware of the work being done by Coko (the Collaborative Knowledge Foundation) in Node.js. What we really craved, though, was a scholarly communications platform written in Python/Django. This was not just a language preference but was also linked to issues around hiring and simplicity, as mentioned above. Python was the most popular programming language in 2017, which would mean that a platform in this language would be comprehensible to a wide range of programmers. So, we chose to write in Python using the Django framework, since this is a well-known, stable, and secure framework for the development of web applications. The platform's ongoing development is funded by a combination of revenue streams: from the OLH, which has begun using the platform as part of a mixed economy of suppliers, and from hosting services that we are providing to others.

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Fleming, Rachel, and Laura Cruz. "Partnerships: The Engaged University and Library Publishing." *OCLC Systems & Services: International Digital Library Perspectives* 31, no. 4 (2015): 196-203. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-02-2014-0017>

Hunter, Ben. "Moving Open Access to Open Source: Transitioning an Open-Access Journal into the Open Journal Systems Journal Management System." *Technical Services Quarterly* 28, no. 1 (2010): 31-40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317131.2010.500972>

Lewis, David W. *Mapping Scholarly Communication Infrastructure: A Bibliographic Scan of Digital Scholarly Communication Infrastructure*. Atlanta, Georgia: Educopia Institute, 2020. <https://educopia.org/mapping-the-scholarly-communication-landscape-bibliographic-scan/>

Loubani, Tarek, Alison Sinclair, Sally Murray, Claire Kendall, Anita Palepu, Anne Marie Todkill, and John Willinsky. "No Budget, No Worries: Free and Open Source Publishing Software in Biomedical Publishing." *Open Medicine* 2, no. 4 (2008): e114-e120. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3091616/>

MacGregor, James, Kevin Stranack, and John Willinsky. "The Public Knowledge Project: Open Source Tools for Open Access to Scholarly Communication." In *Opening Science: The Evolving Guide on How the Internet is Changing Research, Collaboration and Scholarly Publishing*, edited by Sönke Bartling and Sascha Friesike, 165-175. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2014. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-00026-8_11

Maistrovskaya, Mariya, and Kaitlin Newson. "Making the Move to Open Journal Systems 3: Recommendations for a (Mostly) Painless Upgrade." *Code4Lib Journal*, no. 43 (2019). <https://journal.code4lib.org/articles/14260>

From June 2017 to August 2018, Scholars Portal, a consortial service of the Ontario Council of University Libraries, upgraded 10 different multi-journal instances of the Open Journal Systems (OJS) 3 software, building expertise on the upgrade process along the way. The final and the largest instance to be upgraded was the University of Toronto Libraries, which hosts over 50 journals. In this article, we will discuss the upgrade planning and process, problems encountered along the way, and some best practices in supporting journal teams through the upgrade on a multi-journal instance. We will also include checklists and technical troubleshooting tips to help institutions make their upgrade as smooth and worry-free as possible. Finally, we will go over post-upgrade support strategies and next steps in making the most out of your transition to OJS 3.

This article will primarily be useful for institutions hosting instances of OJS 2, but those that have already upgraded, or are considering hosting the software, may find the outlined approach to support and testing helpful.

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Mattson, Mark, and Linda Friend. "A Planning Perspective for Library Journal Publishing Services." *OCLC Systems & Services: International digital library perspectives* 30, no. 3 (2014): 178-191. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OCLC-01-2014-0005>

McHale, Nina. "Open Access Publishing with Drupal." *Code4Lib Journal*, no. 15 (2011). <https://journal.code4lib.org/articles/5913>

In January 2009, the Colorado Association of Libraries (CAL) suspended publication of its print quarterly journal, *Colorado Libraries*, as a cost-saving measure in a time of fiscal uncertainty. Printing and mailing the journal to its 1300 members cost CAL more than \$26,000 per year. Publication of the journal was placed on an indefinite hiatus until the editorial staff proposed an online, open access format a year later. The benefits to migrating to open access included: significantly lower costs; a green platform; instant availability of content; a greater level of access to users with disabilities; and a higher level of visibility of the journal and the association. The editorial staff chose Drupal, including the E-journal module, and while Drupal is notorious for its steep learning curve—which exacerbated delays to content that had been created before the publishing hiatus—the fourth electronic issue was published recently at coloradolibrariesjournal.org. This article will discuss both the benefits and challenges of transitioning to an open access model and the choice Drupal as a platform over other more established journal software options.

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McKiernan, Gerry. "Web-Based Journal Manuscript Management and Peer-Review Software and Systems." *Library Hi Tech News* 19, no. 7 (2002). <https://doi.org/10.1108/lhtn.2002.23919gaf.003>

Ndungu, Miriam Wanjiku. "Publishing with Open Journal Systems (OJS): A Librarian's Perspective." *Serials Review* 46, no. 1 (2020): 21-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2020.1732717>

Odu, Obiajulu, and Aysa Ekanger. "How We Tried to JATS XML." *Ravnetrykk* 39 (2020): 156–162. <https://doi.org/10.7557/15.5517>

This is a story about how an Open Journal Systems-based library publishing service tried (and failed) to implement XML in one of its publications. We ran a small project to look at how journals we support could develop a JATS XML-based publishing workflow using existing open software tools.

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Owen, Brian, And Kevin Stranack. "The Public Knowledge Project and Open Journal Systems: Open Source Options for Small Publishers." *Learned Publishing* 25, no. 2 (2012): 138--144. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20120208>

Ratan, Kristen, Katherine Skinner, Catherine Mitchell, Brandon Locke, and David Pcolar. *Library Publishing Infrastructure: Assembling New Solutions*. Atlanta: Educopia Institute, 2021. <https://educopia.org/nglp-lib-pub-infrastructure/>

This report documents the design, methods, results, and recommendations of the Next Generation Library Publishing (NGLP) project team's 2019-2021 study of library publishing infrastructure gaps and requirements. This research was designed to accomplish two related goals: 1) to reveal and chronicle library publishing stakeholders' current needs, interests, and desires regarding the tools and environments that support their publishing activities, and 2) to develop a meta-understanding of the open-source tools and environments available for publishing, how those tools and environments might be combined and built upon, and where gaps between them might be mitigated through standards, scripts, and documentation.

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Royster, Paul. "Publishing Original Content in an Institutional Repository." *Serials Review* 34, no. 1 (2008): 27-30. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00987913.2008.10765148>

Samuels, Ruth Gallegos, and Henry Griffy. "Evaluating Open Source Software for Use in Library Initiatives: A Case Study Involving Electronic Publishing." *portal: Libraries and the Academy* 12, no. 1 (2012): 41-62. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pla.2012.0007>

Staines, Heather Ruland. "Digital Open Annotation with Hypothesis: Supplying the Missing Capability of the Web." *Journal of Scholarly Publishing* 49, no. 3 (2018): 345-365.
<https://www.utpjournals.press/doi/abs/10.3138/jsp.49.3.04>

Thomas, Sarah E. "Publishing Solutions for Contemporary Scholars: The Library as Innovator and Partner." *Publishing Research Quarterly* 22 (2006): 27-37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12109-006-0013-5>

Willinsky, John. "Toward the Design of an Open Monograph." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 12, no. 1 (2009).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0012.103>

Wodtke, Larissa. "Online Resources for Scholarly Journal Publishing." *Scholarly and Research Communication* 9, no. 1 (2018). <https://src-online.ca/index.php/src/article/view/283>

5.0 Library and University Press Mergers/Partnerships and Other Relevant Works

Adema, Janneke, and Graham Stone. *Changing Publishing Ecologies: A Landscape Study of New University Presses and Academic-Led Publishing*. London: JISC, 2017.
<https://web.archive.org/web/20170904150452/https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6666/1/Changing-publishing-ecologies-report.pdf>

New university presses and scholarly publishing in the library are increasingly playing an important role in the shift of scholarly communications. The US-based Library Publishing Coalition defines these new library-led presses as a "set of activities led by college and university libraries to support the creation, dissemination, and curation of scholarly, creative, and/or educational works." (Skinner et al., 2014; Library Publishing Coalition, 2013). They typically embrace open access, digital first, new business models, enable universities to meet strategic goals including outreach and impact, and facilitate researchers in publishing research outputs.

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Adema, Janneke, and Graham Stone. "The Surge in New University Presses and Academic-Led Publishing: an Overview of a Changing Publishing Ecology in the UK." *LIBER Quarterly* 27, no. 1 (2017): 97-126.
<https://liberquarterly.eu/article/view/10856>

This article outlines the rise and development of New University Presses and Academic-Led Presses in the UK or publishing for the UK market. Based on the Jisc research project, *Changing publishing ecologies: a landscape study of new university presses and academic-led publishing*, commonalities between these two types of presses are identified to better assess their future needs and requirements. Based on this analysis, the article argues for the development of a publishing toolkit, for further research into the creation of a typology of presses and publishing initiatives, and for support with community building to help these initiatives grow and develop further, whilst promoting a more diverse publishing ecology.

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Anderson-Wilk, Mark, and Sue Kunda. "Publisher-Library Partnership for Accessibility: A Case Study of Scholarly Publishing for Public Audiences." *Journal of Electronic Publishing* 15, no. 1 (2012).
<https://doi.org/10.3998/3336451.0015.104>

The Association of American University Presses. *Library-Press Collaboration Survey*: New York, NY, 2013.
<https://web.archive.org/web/20200221162909/http://www.aupresses.org/resources/for-members/data-collection-and-analysis/library-press-collaboration-survey>

Bains, Simon. "The Role of the Library in Scholarly Publishing: The University of Manchester Experience." *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 39, no. 3 (2017): 70-77. <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.380>

The emergence of networked digital methods of scholarly dissemination has transformed the role of the academic library in the context of the research life cycle. It now plays an important role in the dissemination of research outputs (e.g. through repository management and gold open access publication processing) as well as more traditional acquisition and collection management. The University of Manchester Library and Manchester University Press have developed a strategic relationship to consider how they can work in partnership to support new approaches to scholarly publishing. They have delivered two projects to understand researcher and student needs and to develop tools and services to meet these needs. This work has found that the creation of new journal titles is costly and provides significant resourcing challenges and that support for student journals in particular is mixed amongst senior academic administrators. Research has suggested that there is more value to the University in the provision of training in scholarly publishing than in the creation of new in-house journal titles. Where such titles are created, careful consideration of sustainable business models is vital.

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Liverpool University Press and the University of Liverpool Library collaborated to publish two open access monographs to gain insights into each other's processes and requirements, and improve the guidance provided to researchers and authors. Lessons learned include researchers' knowledge of publishing and open access, the monograph publishing process and costs involved, licences and third-party content and the marketing and discoverability of open monographs. Researchers, particularly those at the start of their career, may not have much knowledge and experience of publishing and so it is important for publishers to be as transparent as possible about the processes involved, and for libraries to ensure they are providing sufficient guidance. Knowledge about publishers' processes and costs allows libraries to have a better understanding about what is reasonable to expect and for researchers to better plan costs for funding applications. Transparency from publishers about the types of costs involved, as well as a greater understanding of the financial requirements of libraries and their institutions, will allow publishers to plan their marketing of open monographs more effectively. The project demonstrated that collaboration between libraries and publishers can be extremely valuable and beneficial to both.

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At the University of Ottawa, Canada, the UO Press and the UO Library have developed a strategic partnership to publish and disseminate selected new monographs as gold open access (OA). Starting in 2013, the Library agreed to fund three books at C\$10,000 per book (a total of C\$30,000 per year) in order to remove barriers to accessing scholarship and to align with scholarly communication goals of the University. In 2015 this agreement was renewed for another three years and the funding was increased to cover four books (a total of C\$40,000 per year). Ten titles have so far been published under this model. The data reveals that there have been 12,629 downloads as well as 16,584 page views of these titles, as of September 2015. There have been over 4,700 copies (print and EPUB) sold in spite of the free availability of the PDF version. This program has been very successful in terms of increasing the visibility and impact of the Press's publications; in providing unrestricted access to new scholarly research; and also in providing a significant source of revenue for the Press. The goals, process and outcomes are described in the context of the UO Press and the UO Library.

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BACKGROUND At one-hundred twenty-two articles published, the open access journal *Tremor and Other Hyperkinetic Movements (Tremor)* is growing its readership and expanding its influence among patients, clinicians, researchers, and the general public interested in issues of non-Parkinsonian tremor disorders. Among the characteristics that set the journal apart from similar publications, *Tremor* is published in partnership with the library-based publications program at Columbia University's Center for Digital Research and Scholarship

(CDRS). DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM The production of *Tremor* in conjunction with its editor, a researching faculty member, clinician, and epidemiologist at the Columbia University Medical Center, has pioneered several new workflows at CDRS: article-charge processing, coordination of vendor services, integration into PubMed Central, administration of publication scholarships granted through a patient-advocacy organization, and open source platform development among them. Open access publishing ventures in libraries often strive for lean operations by attempting to capitalize on the scholarly impact available through the use of templated and turnkey publication systems. For CDRS, production on *Tremor* has provided opportunity to build operational capacity for more involved publication needs. The following report introduces a framework and account of the costs of producing such a publication as a guide to library and other non-traditional publishing operations interested in gauging the necessary investments. Following a review of the literature published to date on the costs of open access publishing and of the practice of journal publishing in academic libraries, the authors present a brief history of *Tremor* and a tabulation of the costs and expenditure of effort by library staff in production. NEXT STEPS Although producing *Tremor* has been more expensive than other partner publications in the center's portfolio, the experiences have improved the library's capacity for addressing more challenging projects, and developments for *Tremor* have already begun to be applied to other journals.

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BACKGROUND The University of Arizona Press moved under the University of Arizona Library both physically and administratively a few years ago, echoing a trend amongst university presses: 20 AAUP members now are under the administration of university libraries. To understand the new evolving relationships in scholarly communication, a review of university press and library collaborations was undertaken by the University of Arizona Press and the University of Arizona Library through the Association of Research Libraries Career Enhancement Program (ARL CEP). LITERATURE REVIEW There has been much written throughout the years on both the acrimonious and collaborative relationships between university presses and academic libraries. Much of the literature includes either editorials or case studies, with one or two major reviews of scholarly communications and the state of publishing. DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT During the course of nine weeks, the ARL CEP Fellow reviewed existing literature, interviewed staff at the University of Arizona Press and Library, and conducted 27 informal interviews with library deans, press directors, and scholarly communications leaders. The interviews addressed the partnership history, structure, motivations, goals and needs, administrative support and budget decisions, key stakeholders, and thoughts on the future of their relationships as well as scholarly communications. Then University of Arizona Library and Press staff were interviewed regarding their perceptions of their roles and each other's roles. NEXT STEPS This research report includes findings from the literature review and interviews as well as specific recommendations for the University of Arizona that will be implemented to improve and build relationships going forward.

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INTRODUCTION The journal publishing service at the University of Florida George A. Smathers Libraries is structured to use a team-based approach that integrates subject specialists across the library. DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM Since 2012, the UF Libraries have worked in partnership with a number of scholarly societies to publish their research. The focus, to date, of academic library publishing on institutional publications belies potential partnerships with scholarly societies and organizations external to the library's institution. Services provided, challenges faced, and examples of successful publishing partnerships with UF Libraries are described. The team approach enables the library to be innovative and nimble in response to publishing opportunities. Scholarly societies most interested in entering publishing contracts with the Libraries publishing program are those that share aspects of the library mission such as accessibility and innovation. NEXT STEPS Academic library publishing offers unique partnership opportunities for scholarly societies and external organizations that are mutually beneficial and that complement library publishing of institutional material.

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INTRODUCTION This article describes a joint open textbook publishing initiative begun in 2013 between Oregon State University (OSU) Libraries and Press and the Open Educational Resources and Emerging Technologies unit of Oregon State University's Extended Campus. **DESCRIPTION OF PROGRAM** This initiative combines the Open Access values and project management resources of OSU Libraries, the book production (peer review, editing, design, marketing) expertise of OSU Press, and the technological development skills of the Open Educational Resources and Emerging Technologies unit. Authored by OSU faculty and focused across some of the University's signature areas, the initiative seeks to establish a sustainable model for research libraries and university presses to collaborate with each other and other partners to publish open textbooks that will benefit students on both economic and educational levels. The article analyzes how open textbooks fit within the emerging library publishing movement, examines the implementation of the OSU open textbook publishing initiative, and conveys some lessons learned for other libraries to consider as they entertain the possibility of similar collaborations. **NEXT STEPS** A description of next steps includes tracking course adoptions of the textbooks as well as establishing sustainable digital publishing platforms and business models.

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This report, prepared for SPARC Europe, sketches the landscape of university-based not-for-profit publishing in Europe with a primary focus on open access publishing of journals. It provides a view of the different types of initiatives in terms of their size, operational and business models, technologies used, stakeholder involvement, concentration of scientific fields, growth, as well as regional characteristics and recommendations for SPARC Europe and DOAJ.

The report attests to a rich and continuously evolving ecology of open access publishing initiatives in universities in Europe and elsewhere. Beyond the commercial publishing models, it appears that university libraries are largely the foci of intense activity in journal publishing and books (primarily where a university press exists), while national governments are moving towards building national collections, national portals and services paid for by public funds to make research published within the country more relevant and accessible internationally. This ecology is primarily populated by small publishers who are largely invisible, and much smaller numbers of large and medium-sized university-based activities. At the same time, a growing number of innovative initiatives in the University and outside, mostly initiated by scholars and University Presses, eager to experiment in developing a fair and sustainable scholarly communications system, attests to a vibrant and swiftly-evolving landscape.

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This article presents an overview of a strategic partnership undertaken by the Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN) and the Érudit Consortium (Érudit) to support the move towards open access for Canadian francophone scholarly journals.

CRKN and Érudit have had a relationship through a traditional commercial subscription model since 2008. In 2014, the two organizations recognized the need for a new relationship that would address two major challenges: the fragility of the Canadian not-for-profit scholarly publishing environment and the increasing pressure from libraries and funding agencies for scholarly journals to move towards open access. Érudit and CRKN have worked collaboratively to create an innovative partnership, which provides a framework for a new relationship between publishers and libraries, and helps to provide financial support to Canadian publishers during the transition to a fully open access model.

This paper presents the perspectives of the two organizations involved in the partnership by outlining the common goals, objectives, and strategy, as well as the differing needs and perspectives of libraries and publishers. It summarizes the key aspects of the partnership as well as the challenges faced. Through this case study, the authors demonstrate how university libraries can play an active role in working with journals to support open access to research.

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